

TEACHING EDUCATION WITH TECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS AND TEACHING THEM HOW TO USE

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Annotation: In this thesis it is given that every person has a unique set of bilingual traits; it might be difficult to sum up bilingualism in a few words. There could be disparities in a language's aptitude and use, or in the level of expertise between the two languages. Most people learn to speak two languages because they find it useful in their daily activities. As a result, each person's level of bilingualism will be unique. Although it is relatively typical to have a dominant language, bilinguals are not always completely fluent in both of their languages. It should be mentioned that learning to communicate in two languages takes time. One cannot become bilingual after studying a language for six months. Information on bilingualism hypothesis is included in this article.

Abstract: Course books are the most popular way to learn foreign languages. However, in the 21st century, there are other ways to learn languages, such as multimedia tools. The use of the Internet, newspapers, radio, or television can be an alternative to traditional language learning methods. The rapid advancement of science and technology, such as multimedia technology, has made it possible to explore this new teaching method more effectively. In reality, multimedia technology plays a vital role in the teaching of English language, particularly in the context of non-native speaking English.

This article investigates the effectiveness of multimedia tools in enhancing the development of receptive skills (listening and reading comprehension) in foreign language learning. It explores the advantages of multimedia resources, including increased engagement, improved motivation, and exposure to authentic language. The paper examines various multimedia tools such as audio recordings, video clips, interactive websites, and educational software. Additionally, it discusses pedagogical strategies for integrating these tools into classroom instruction, focusing on activities that promote active listening and close reading

What it means to communicate in two languages cannot be easily defined. Does this encompass speaking, listening, reading, and writing? How well should the person be able to communicate? How effectively does the person need to communicate? The meaning of being bilingual is mostly up to the speakers themselves. Bilingualism is prevalent in many cultures all over the world. Depending on the circumstances surrounding someone's bilingualism, examples

of nearly every language combination can be found. Access to quality education is still a major bottleneck in developing countries. Efforts at opening the access to a large majority of citizens in developing nations have explored different strategies including the use of multimedia technology. This paper provides a systematic review of different multimedia tools in the teaching and learning processes with a view to examining how multimedia technologies have proven to be a veritable strategy for bridging the gap in the provision of unrestricted access to quality education and improved learners' performance. The review process includes conducting an extensive search of relevant scientific literature, selection of relevant studies using a pre-determined inclusion criteria, literature analysis, and synthesis of the findings of the various studies that have investigated how multimedia have been used for learning and teaching processes. The review examines various case study reports of multimedia tools, their success and limiting factors, application areas, evaluation methodologies, technology components, and age groups targeted by the tools. Future research directions are also provided. Apart from text and images, existing tools were found to have multimedia components such as audio, video, animation and 3-D. The study concluded that the majority of the multimedia solutions deployed for teaching and learning target the solution to the pedagogical content of the subject of interest and the user audience of the solution while the success of the different multimedia tools that have been used on the various target groups and subjects can be attributed to the technologies and components embedded in their development.

Privacy - people who are bilingual have the ability to code-switch. If two bilingual friends found themselves in a situation where they didn't want the people around them to understand what they were talking about, they could code-switch from one language to the other in order to keep their conversation private.

The capacity to switch between various languages or language variations during a single verbal encounter is known as code-switching. Greater cultural awareness – Because culture and language are frequently so closely related, speaking more than one language may enable the speaker to get a deeper understanding of other cultures. For instance, a child who was born to Spanish parents and raised in England but who is proficient in both Spanish and English may have a much stronger knowledge of their Spanish background than a youngster who only speaks English. As a result of being bilingual, this youngster

would probably have a strong understanding of both their Spanish ancestry and British culture.

Job market competition – as we have already seen, language skills are crucial in both corporate and professional contexts. Being bilingual gives people a competitive edge over their monolingual rivals and distinguishes them by enabling them to connect with more coworkers and clients. Third-language acquisition is simple; like with anything, practice makes perfect. It is significantly simpler to study a third language if you are already fluent in two others.

Bilinguals have the rare capacity to combine the best aspects of the two languages they speak, which allows for creative expression. Bilinguals can add powerful words from other languages to their speech to give it more punch with a little bit of imaginative code-switching. Idiomatic language and other expressions in one language occasionally do not translate well into others. Being bilingual allows the speaker to continue using these powerful words and phrases without having to translate them to make sense.

The language system, which some linguists now refer to as implicit linguistic competence, or the grammar, is what is typically impaired as a result of lesions in the perisylvian classical language areas of the left cerebral hemisphere, and this is what neurolinguists and language pathologists have traditionally focused on. Additionally, the majority of second-language curriculum is likewise based on this linguistic system. But in recent years, it has come to more and more attention that language, as currently defined, is only one aspect of verbal communication.

Learning more than one language does not have any notably negative consequences on kids. However, on a functional level, there are certain benefits and drawbacks. People who are bilingual believe that one of the two languages they speak predominates. Even if they learnt the two languages simultaneously, this is always the case. They will therefore always have to exert more mental effort when speaking the secondary language. Additionally, they exert greater effort when speaking the second language, which is reflected in their performance. However, bilinguals nonetheless differ from monolingual speakers in specific ways even when they speak their dominant language.

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